

Open-source methods for DNA manipulation in a cloud lab

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Abstract

Automating biological research has the potential to improve reproducibility, throughput, and free-up scientist time to design rather than execute experiments. One avenue for scientists to leverage automation is through the use of cloud labs. However, there is no publicly available open source code to conduct basic life science workflows in cloud labs, and resources to learn the code are very limited, creating an enormous barrier to entry to cloud science.

Here we present the first ever set of validated, open source protocols for cloud labs. We have developed a full pipeline for manipulating DNA on Emerald Cloud Lab's platform, including onboarding samples, conducting PCR and Golden Gate reactions, and assessing the quality of samples with purification and gel electrophoresis. Each script is open source and available on GitHub, and we also provide instructions and screencast videos for future users. This work represents a necessary first step toward enabling cloud labs to mature into a widely accessible tool for life sciences.

Introduction

Cloud labs are automated remote facilities that allow researchers to design, execute, and analyze experiments remotely. They build upon concepts from cloud computing, aiming to democratize access to cutting-edge equipment, enable scalable and on-demand resource utilization, and provide codified tooling that can be run repeatedly. These capabilities are especially impactful in the life sciences, where experimentation requires time-consuming human labor, reproducibility is difficult, and experimental data is both scarce and valuable. Cloud labs hope to revolutionize the landscape of biological research by enabling scientists to conduct experiments repeatedly, scalably, and remotely.

However, before cloud labs can improve complex life science workflows, more robust foundational software for executing key low-level experimental tasks is required. DNA manipulation and cloning are central to biological engineering, underpinning the molecular mechanisms that enable the precise control and design of biological systems.

In this paper, we present a set of open source scripts for manipulating DNA at Emerald Cloud Lab (ECL). This includes onboarding synthesized primers, conducting PCR, purifying DNA and quantifying DNA concentration, conducting Golden Gate assembly, and assessing size distribution of DNA using gel electrophoresis. These protocols can serve as a starting point for many future biological engineering workflows in the cloud. Our DNA manipulation workflow comprises the in vitro portion of molecular cloning, thus laying the groundwork for future cell-based cloud lab protocols in both bacterial and eukaryotic systems. Due to limitations in working with cells on ECL's platform, we utilized cell-free assay to express DNA, which can then be employed for various biochemical property measurements. Here, we present various biochemical property measurements.

Methods of DNA manipulation

There are numerous techniques for manipulating DNA, as well as various methods for conducting quality control on the resulting samples. Table 1 includes the methods that were developed during the course of this challenge.

See below for more detail on the methods, tips for using them, and links to video walkthroughs.

CloudLab TIP

The cloud provides tons of metadata! Fortunately, this can be used to help you troubleshoot. See this [video](#) and [script](#) for tips on how to effectively troubleshoot in the cloud.

Method	Status
Onboarding synthesized DNA and ordering reagents	
PCR	
Magnetic Bead Purification	
Qubit DNA Quantification Hamilton	
Gel Electrophoresis	
Golden Gate Assembly	
Sanger Sequencing	
Qubit Assay on Echo	
Golden Gate on Echo	

Table 1: Methods for DNA manipulation and current development status.

passing

development started but not yet complete

Onboarding DNA and ordering assay components

GitHub

[link to script](#)

YouTube

[link to screencast](#)

ECL's Documentation

[link 1](#) [link 2](#)

Modifications needed to use the script:

The user will need to provide their own sequences when uploading the Molecular/Oligomer.

Potential pitfalls and known issues:

1. Once you have placed the order with IDT, follow up with ECL to confirm. Make sure you can create the **DropShipTransaction** to track the receiving of your DNA samples.
2. For assay components, once you place the order on Command Center, it automatically creates a transaction to track.

CloudLab TIP

When transferring liquid from one container to another on a Hamilton automated liquid handler, make sure to transfer at least 2uL and ensure there is at least 20uL volume in the source container for the containers we have used in these scripts. It is important to centrifuge the source container if the volume is less than 200uL to avoid having any liquid stuck to the walls of the container.

PCR

GitHub

[link to script](#)

ECL's Documentation

[link 1](#)

Development notes:

The underlying software was designed to source components from the user's inventory, which may or may not contain enough liquid due to the history of the aliquot and evaporation. This can result in PCR reactions lacking the correct final volumes.

Another common issue is the accuracy of volume measurements taken at the end of protocol using ultrasonic method. Volumes less than 100uL and liquids with different surface tension properties to water cannot reliably be measured using the ultrasonic method and the **MeasureVolume** function. When volumes are automatically validated with an ultrasonic ping after completion of a PCR, this can result in the sample's volume being updated to an incorrect, very low value, which causes subsequent steps to fail unnecessarily.

In general, it is best practice to set **MeasureVolume = False** for any sample less than 50uL in volume. We experimented with the accuracy of ultrasonic volume measurement by pipetting 50uL in each well of a 96 well PCR plate and subsequently measuring the volume using ultrasonic volume measurement. The average measurement was 38uL with the lowest being 32uL and highest being 42uL. This indicated that ultrasonic measurement can be unreliable, especially for lower volumes.

Modifications needed to use the script:

1. Use your own samples for **InputSamples**.
2. Modify the parameters like extension time, denaturation/ melting temperature etc, according to your own DNA.

Potential pitfalls and known issues:

1. Specify **MeasureVolume -> False** in order to not lose any sample. This applies specifically to low reaction volumes.
2. It is best to let the PCR plate cool down at room temperature, then perform a brief centrifuge step (2 min at 2000 rpm) to make sure any condensed liquid on the lid/cover is combined into the solution.
3. Larger PCR reaction volumes (> 50uL) will experience fewer errors.

Magnetic bead purification

GitHub

[link to script](#)

ECL's Documentation

[link 1](#)

Development notes:

This protocol did not have any options to control the height from which the loading, washing and elution supernatants were aspirated out of from the wells of the plates. The default options for these were unrealistic. In one case, the aspiration position was 1cm above the bottom of the well, resulting in 0uL elution volumes. Additionally, the original magnets that ECL used were not the most commonly used magnets for automated protocols. After ECL modified the protocol function enable control of the position of aspiration, the results from the **MagneticBeadSeparation** were more reliable. ECL has recently obtained a stronger magnet that may allow for better separation for protocols run in future.

Modifications needed to use the script:

1. Users need to supply their own AmpureXP Magnetic Beads (or other suitable magnetic beads) and samples.
2. Depending on the beads and sample type, users need to modify the loading, washing and elution steps accordingly.

Potential pitfalls and known issues:

1. Make sure the beads and samples are in a Hamilton/ liquid handler compatible container. You can get an appropriate container for your working volume using the **PreferredContainer** function and specifying the option **LiquidHandlerCompatible -> True**.
2. Including the step to mix the beads before beginning the Magnetic Bead Separation protocol is usually very helpful for preventing the beads from settling to the bottom of the container.
3. Ensure the model of the magnetic beads have the field **SampleHandling -> Slurry** so that the beads are mixed before transfer.
4. Experiment with the **AspirationPositionOffset** parameter to ensure you remove all of the supernatant and wash buffers.

Qubit DNA quantification on Hamilton

GitHub

[link to script](#)

ECL's Documentation

[link 1](#)

Development notes:

Initially the transfer of the high concentration Qubit standard was unreliable because ECL did not consider the appropriate dead volume when calculating the amount of Qubit standard to prealiquot to an automation compatible tube on the Hamilton. By aliquoting a larger amount of Qubit standard (allowing for up to 50% dead volume) in advance and using this during the pre-aliquoted standard during the protocol, the liquid transfers became much more reliable.

Modifications needed to use the script:

1. Users need to provide their own samples.
2. This protocol can easily be used with the Qubit RNA BR and HS kits by changing the excitation and emission spectra, switching to the appropriate standards and providing the premixed dilution buffer with the relevant nucleic acid binding dye.

Potential pitfalls and known issues:

1. In order to reduce the time it takes to complete the protocol and avoid having samples/reagents transferred to other containers, have them in Hamilton/ liquid handling compatible containers. Use **ExperimentAliquot** to do this before the start of the experiment. Having bulk reagents in Liquid Handler compatible instruments reduces the time to iterate the experiment.
2. Make sure the samples have enough volume and are in Hamilton/ liquid handling compatible containers to avoid any errors during runtime.

Gel electrophoresis

GitHub

[link to script](#)

ECL's Documentation

[link 1](#)

Development notes:

The gel electrophoresis protocol development was plagued by several issues. The default parameters for sample preparation and loading dyes resulted in sample transfer inconsistencies. These inconsistencies stemmed from the preparation of sample and loading dye volumes that did not account for pipeting error. Rather than mix exactly the amount required to load (8uL total), the ECL team advised us to prepare a total sample volume of 20uL. This seems to have resolved the issue of unsuccessful loading. Additionally, adding a brief centrifugation step helped in loading of the gel.

Another issue was that the default loading dyes were not appropriate for the given use case because the size of the DNA fragment coincided with the standard size in one of the dyes.

Modifications needed to use the script:

1. The user needs to provide their own samples and any control samples.
2. The user can modify the total sample preparation volume by modifying the loading dye volumes and dilution buffer volume.
3. Pick the right analytical gel to use from the list provided.
4. Choose the right loading dyes for your DNA size.

Potential pitfalls and known issues:

1. Loading could fail if the prepared volume is left at the default of 8uL (sample+loading dyes+dilution buffer). A total loading volume of 20uL leads to successful loading.
2. Including the centrifuge step could also help ensure successful loading.

Golden Gate assembly

GitHub

[link to script](#)

YouTube

[link to screencast](#)

ECL's Documentation

[link 1](#)

Golden Gate Assembly Script Workflow

Figure 1: Strategy and results of golden gate assembly.

Development notes:

The overall strategy for this protocol (Figure 1) involves conducting a golden gate reaction in 96-well plates, followed by the addition of PCR components directly to the original plate and amplifying the linear assembled construct (Figure 2). This strategy has previously been used to assemble linear constructs for cell free protein synthesis (DOI: 10.1126/scitranslmed.abn1252). Note that this usage differs from the most common use of golden gate as a reaction preceding transformation of a circular construct into bacteria.

The first issues encountered were related to the volumes of Bsal and T4 Ligase. For a 20uL reaction, it needed 1uL of each reagent. It is difficult to reliably transfer 1uL on ECL's platform. To eliminate ultra-small volume liquid handling steps, both reagents were diluted 2x with nuclease-free water and reactions were initiated with 2uL of each reagent.

Another issue was the design of the constructs themselves. While we originally tried a three part reaction, we later simplified it to a two part reaction, with improved results.

In an early development step, a small amount of the golden gate reaction product was removed from the golden gate plate and added to a second PCR plate as a template. This was unreliable due to small volume pipetting. To overcome this issue, we added PCR master mix and primers directly to the original plate. This resulted in better amplification.

Modifications needed to use the script:

1. The users need to have their own constructs to assemble via golden gate assembly.
2. The length of incubation for the golden gate should be adjusted based on the number of fragments in the assembly ([NEB recommendation](#)).
3. The script performs two golden gate assembly reactions. The users can increase or decrease this according to their needs.
4. The `ExperimentPCR` and `ExperimentGelElectrophoresis` parameters need to be modified according to the user's DNA size.

Potential pitfalls and known issues:

1. Make sure you have enough volumes of reagents in liquid handler compatible containers.
2. Bsal and T4 Ligase needs to be diluted appropriately in order to avoid adding less than 2 uL of volume into the reaction.

Methods of protein manipulation

We aimed to develop flexible, modular protocols and robust software solutions to facilitate cloud lab research. In vitro protein engineering was an attractive option for a modular workflow (Figure 3). This is because it is composed of three modules (DNA assembly, protein expression, and biochemical measurement), each of which is interspersed with standard sample types of purified DNA or protein that can pass thorough quality control protocols. In addition to developing protocols for DNA manipulation (previous section), we also explored developing protocols for protein production and measurement in vitro.

Protein	Status
Resuspension of Protein	✓
AlphaLISA	🔧
His Bead Purification	🔧
His Bead Recharge	🔧
Other	
MassSpec of small molecule	✓
FPLC	🔧

Table 2: Methods for Protein Assays and current development status.

- ✓ passing
- 🔧 some testing performed
- 🔧 development started but not yet complete

Figure 3: Modularity of in vitro protein engineering workflows.

Resuspension of protein

GitHub

[link to script](#)

ECL's Documentation

[link 1](#)

Resuspension of a lyophilized protein sample requires gentle, yet thorough mixing in order to reconstitute the protein without introducing aeration into the sample. Special care is required with automated protocols to ensure that protein samples are handled appropriately. A major issue we encountered in protein resuspension was overly aggressive mixing that led to significant aeration of the sample and subsequent inaccurate volume measurements. In order to resolve this issue, we altered the default mixing parameters to specify that mixing be performed manually using a pipette to limit the force applied to the sample (**MixType** -> **Pipette**). We also set the mix volume to half the total volume to reduce the chances of aerating the sample (**MixVolume** -> (**0.5*total volume**)). It was also important to ensure mixing was thorough and that all lyophilized protein was resuspended. This was accomplished with **MixUntilDissolved** -> **True**.

Modifications needed to use the script:

1. The user needs to provide their own lyophilized protein sample and desired reconstitution buffer.
2. Modify the resuspension volume according to the desired final concentration.

Potential pitfalls and known issues:

1. Bubbles can form in the protein vial during resuspension. Make sure you check the appearance of the sample post resuspension to make sure the suspension looks clear.
2. If bubbles are formed during resuspension, the measured volume will be incorrect. To fix this problem, the user could perform centrifugation to get rid of them before measuring the volume. A centrifugation step is included in the GitHub script.
3. The user should measure absorbance (A280) after resuspension to ensure the concentration of protein is correct before proceeding with downstream experiments. An absorbance measurement step is included in the GitHub script.

Methods requiring further development

- Golden Gate assembly and Qubit assay on echo (acoustic liquid handler) were under development. The sample source plates (echo compatible) plates were prepared by transferring reagents and samples in them.
- A few troubleshooting and optimization runs have been performed for protein purification using His-tagged beads. Some parameters needed further modification followed by subsequent testing.
- A few troubleshooting runs were performed for AlphaLISA experiment however results were not reproducible. Parameters and the script needs to be optimized to work with low volume.
- Protein separation using FPLC is under development by the ECL's Scientific Solutions team.

Please reach out if you would like access to the scripts for further development and/or optimization.

Conclusion

In this project, we developed the first ever set of open-source scripts for conducting cloud science on the Emerald Cloud Lab platform. Our pipeline for DNA manipulation includes key steps such as onboarding synthesized DNA, performing key reactions like Golden Gate assembly and PCR, and conducting quality control using gel electrophoresis. The scripts are publicly available on GitHub, with accompanying video walkthroughs for additional background information. During development, one common challenge we encountered was the difficulty of small volume pipetting, which significantly impacted the structure of our protocols. This work provides a starting point for the community to build upon and establishes guidelines for best practices unique to cloud science, including sample disposal at the end of scripts.

DNA manipulation forms the basis of many workflows in biological engineering. We anticipate that one direction our open-source code will be expanded to is cell-free protein engineering. In the future, these DNA manipulation techniques could be applied to a variety of cell-based assays, including pathway engineering in bacteria and experiments in mammalian cells. Investing in the creation of open-source protocols like these is essential for removing barriers to cloud lab science, and may one day enable it to become a mainstream approach that redefines how we conduct research.